

**DISTRIBUTED INFORMATION ENVIRONMENT
FOR DEFENSE INFORMATION SYSTEM NETWORK (DISN)- FAR TERM**

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INTRODUCTION

The intent of this paper is to give the reader an overview of the expanding relationships that Rome Laboratory and other service laboratories are pursuing that portend great changes in the way they do business, their inter- relationships, and how they all will effect the insertion of new technologies into the Distributed Information Environment that will be the DISN-Far Term. The first topic to be considered is the Joint Directors of Laboratories' (JDL) role in support of Defense Information Infrastructure (DII). The second part of this paper will discuss an alliance that Rome Laboratory is making with regional commercial and academic counterparts that will also impact networking R&D.

**JOINT DIRECTORS OF
LABORATORIES (JDL)**

The JDL is comprised of several technical panels but the focus of this paper is on the Technology Panel for C3 (TPC3) and specifically its' subpanel on Communications Networks. The Air Force's Rome Laboratory, Griffiss AFB, NY, Army's Center for Communications (CECOM), Ft. Monmouth, NJ and the Naval Research and Development (NRaD)

Center in San Diego, CA share the responsibility to coordinate service expenditures of exploratory and advanced development dollars. Their purpose is to eliminate duplication and enhance collaboration. Other than the obvious money saving value of this jointness, a major goal is to avoid interoperability problems when technologies are immature and easily changed.

As previous stated, the focus of this subpanel is communications networks. As a result of the information explosion in support of C2I, particularly for data and imagery, future, military communications networking technologies have to be able to support a wide variety of old and new information services under stressed, wartime environments. These services go well beyond those currently deployed in the field. Multimedia workstations typify the new class of user terminals, forcing a fundamental change in the communications technology needed in future networks such as DISN. Security and survivability, likewise, pose vital design concerns so that security "air gaps" can be eliminated and communications made more enduring through the use of technologies like multi-band networking. CECOM, NRaD and RL have defined three classes of integrated (multi-media) communications

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"subnetworks" that will be necessary for joint, theater communications. These are point-to-point, mobile and broadcast networks. Each of these networks form a crucial part in extending the worldwide DISN backbone to a theater of conflict in support of the National Command Authorities. This ability to provide "seamless" communications across the broad theater and tactical networking environment is pivotal to effective, worldwide C2. Each service laboratory is engaged in the development of technologies aimed at meeting this future goal. Under the auspices of this panel, these efforts comprise a significant portion of the DOD research and development program aimed at developing military networking technology for the next century. Each laboratory has taken lead-service responsibility for the 6.2 and 6.3A R&D in the specific subnetworking area where they possess the most expertise and the majority of requirements. The negotiations under Project Reliance produced the following partitioning of R&D responsibilities;

Air Force - Wide area subnetworks comprised primarily of point-to-point media and characterized by low to high bandwidth links.

Army- Local area, mobile ground subnetworks.

Navy - Wide area subnetworks comprised primarily of broadcast media and characterized by low bandwidth links.

Coordination of these research and development initiatives is important

Therefore, the panel conducts a series of yearly workshops as a forum in which the their programs can be closely coordinated at the working level to facilitate interoperability and share common R&D

tasks. "User" organizations, such as DISA, play an important role in establishing long term architectures which these technologies must support and therefore, participate heavily in these workshops.

NYNET NETWORK R&D

In recent years, Research and Development (R&D) in communications networking has received considerable emphasis in business and government sparked by the rapid growth in the needs of the information industry and the capabilities offered by fiber optics. Fiber optic cable technology has enabled the creation of a national, gigabit transmission infrastructure whose bandwidth and performance properties far exceed its electronic counterparts. This advance, however, has generated the need for corollary research and development in several critical areas. These are: information services, Asynchronous Transfer Mode (ATM) switching, network management, protocols/routing and simulation technologies for high fidelity analysis and assessment of complex network performance parameters. These needs however, are national needs and have generated interest in the commercial and military R&D communities. At Rome Laboratory a regional alliance has been formed with NYNEX, Cornell University, Syracuse University, Columbia University and Polytechnic University of NY to collaborate on information technologies. As part of this alliance, New York Telephone has provided a high speed computing/communications corridor that gives OC-3 (155Mbps) connectivity initially with future enhancements possible up to OC-48 (2.48Gbs). This corridor, called NYNET, will serve as a backbone for information technologies experiments amongst the participants. The following is a discussion of the areas for collaboration.

Information Services - The ability of consumers to gain access to information of all types and to collaboratively interact among physically disbursed colleagues will be a hallmark application available on future communications networks. These capabilities are equally pertinent to corporate management as well as military command and control (C²) applications. The defining parameter for these services is the quantity and quality of the underlying communications ready to support these services. In communications, the trend is towards higher bandwidth and performance. This permits the definition of radically new information services that can be offered to the user that will be far from the conventional telephone, video and data services now tendered. There exists an important need to establish an experimental infrastructure on which these future services can be designed and prototyped before pilot demonstrations are offered in commercial and military networks. The high speed, NYNET corridor will provide that infrastructure so that the participants can collaboratively design, develop and experiment with new information services.

Switching - ATM switches are being developed rapidly and, even before complete standards are available, there is a need for a capability to experiment with the various approaches to ATM design and to establish a platform to develop protocols, experiment with performance over non-fiber bearers and develop strategies and designs for interoperability. These activities will require collaboration among several sites over the corridor. Another project that will be conducted over the corridor will involve the creation of a wide area ATM based network across the central region of NY. This program will be a model of how a military ATM network will be an extension of the commercial network as represented by the corridor. Experiments will include the use of

encryption devices currently under development in DoD, the design and demonstration of multi-media services for disbursed command and control, the introduction of military like transmission anomalies outside the corridor to study their effects on services and protocols, interoperability among diverse ATM designs, network management across commercial and military domains, the interactive relationship between network management and distributed computing systems, and service conversion between incompatible providers.

Network Management - Advanced network management techniques need to be developed to manage high speed networks where problems of flow control, buffering, data latency and congestion prevention schema become significant due to the high information transfer rates. To be truly survivable, the intelligence within a network must be capable of making instantaneous decisions that are accurate. (In this instance, network intelligence refers to the network management and network control). In a high speed network, many of these problems are exacerbated by the amount of data that can exist within the network at any given time (data latency). The technical challenges arise out of the fact that within the network structure there is little homogeneity, the vital characteristics of the network are constantly changing, threats will come from within (disgruntled employee or, in the military, the captured node) and the physical expanse of a network is enormous. Effectively, the adaptive network management and control turns the network into an intelligent subnet capable of reacting in such a way as to self-heal all infliction either from threats or traffic surges. However, these decisions will be made with less than perfect information regarding the status of the network at any given time. Artificial Intelligence (AI) will

be used extensively to solve distributed resource allocation problems and Natural Intelligence (NI) will be used to spot trends and isolate patterns associated with induced threats or failures. In this research area the real survivability of the network will be illustrated by creating a situation in which dispersed portions of the network undergo destruction and disruption while the information services being provided across the network remains relatively stable. The capabilities to be demonstrated include: real-time connectivity restoral via multiple media, negotiated restoral between commercial and defense networks, allocation of traffic responsibilities between the space and terrestrial transmission assets, information service management including real-time service modification, as well as real-time development and enforcement of service or information policies. All these concerns apply to commercial and military networks and the proposed corridor will enable cooperative research and effective transition of these developments to both communities.

Protocols/Routing - Associate with these services are the communications protocols that create and maintain them under various communications anomalies. The design of high speed, robust protocols and service related protocols such as multi-casting will be an area of endeavor for this corridor. The transmission characteristics of the corridor will be of such a high quality as to preclude current design approaches that must account for error producing anomalies. Current designs incorporate significant overhead in data transmission that will not be necessary in the corridor. Collaborative research will focus on the design and performance assessment of streamlined protocols. Robust protocol research will address issues that are created at interface points to external networks where capacity will be less and error conditions worse.

Simulation of Network Performance -

The determination of network performance is a complex analytical process often mathematically intractable in nature due to the interdependencies intrinsic in the processes that comprise network behavior. This has led to the use of simulation of networks using computer simulation tools. However, given the constraints in processing speed, the level of fidelity in these models is often sacrificed. Access to supercomputers over the corridor, give networking researchers a valuable tools with which to conduct highly accurate simulations of networks. The degree of fidelity could be so sufficient that simulated networks could be made to operate real-time, in serial with operational networks.

SUMMARY

With DISN as a focus for future DoD networking R&D needs, firm alliances among the three services for joint, cooperative R&D and effective partnerships with industry and the academic communities the time has never been better for making major advances in the information infrastructure that will support command and control of the future.